

Women's Education And Social Development: A Makeover From Traditionalism Towards Modernism During Pre-Independent India

Dr. Andrey Shastri

Amity University Lucknow

Received: May 15, 2025

Accepted: Jun 14, 2025

Published: Jun 22, 2025

Abstract

India is a world and a land and a country famous for its ancient culture. It represents different human races, different cultures, and religions that hold its space and strives for political and cultural supremacy. India inhabits the cradle of a great civilization. The Indian education system is very unique and it's not wrong to take pride in, an ancient and age-long educational system. The status of women in any society surely examines the social organization of that particular society. Somewhere education and women's status are closely interrelated. Education acts as a major instrument of change and development in any society. Modern education for women in India began in the early years of the nineteenth century. Earlier the necessity of women's education was not felt. The article put a major focus on the growth of women's education and how they overcome from their traditional images, and convert themselves into a 'New Modern Woman'.

Keywords: women, education, literate, modern, status, development.

Introduction

This paper is considered a slice of women's educational development from the 1900s to the 1947s, a small part of a larger study. However, mentioned very early that through the advancement in education, an improvement in women's social status can be generally accompanied. 'The movement for improving women's status all over the world has always emphasized education as the most significant instrument for changing women's subjugated position in society' (Kamat 1976, p3). India being a multicultural land has the right to take pride in, an ancient and age-long educational system. Dr. F.W. Thomas, one of the most distinguished Indologists writes that there has been no country where the love of learning had so early an origin or has exercised so lasting and powerful an influence (Mukherji, 1951, p2). Earlier also the motto of education looked to the development of a particular individual which enables them to lead a good life. Even the aim of modern education was also towards the

betterment of an individual. Earlier also we had very few literate women or educated women around us. Definitely their number were very small. As there was no particular organized provision for educating women. Education in India under the British government according to Howell, 'was first ignored, then violently and successfully opposed, then conducted on a system now universally admitted to be erroneous and finally placed on its present footing.'(Mukherji, 1951,p5).

During the colonial era Britishers had very less interest in girls' education. As they were only concerned to educate only a few masses which could help them in their administration work. They focussed on the English language. This is the reason that in most of the school's medium was English. It becomes the medium of instruction. The diminishing of the pre-British system of education in the country is universal. The establishment of the British empire and the chasing of the colonial economic and political policies, somewhere it gave a death blow to the indigenous system of education. Somewhere it was believed that the loss of the indigenous system of education was continuing as it did not get the proper support of the Indians somehow themselves. Many of the educated personalities viewed modern education as a mode of liberation and totally had rational thinking. In fact, in the coming years, there was a demand for the expansion of the English system of education.

From the company's charter in 1813 till the well-known Hunter Commission of 1881, women's education did not rise. Indian Education (Hunter) Commission reviewed the progress of education in India and several efforts had been in terms of women's education. This Commission recommended more liberal grant-in-aid for girl's schools than for boys and provisions for special scholarships and different prizes for girls were made. Basically, Indian Education Commission of 1882 examined the question on the education of women and brought it into the limelight and came to the conclusion that female education was in an extremely backward condition, and in fact, they should receive a large number of funds for their development. In short, the commission also suggested the introduction of a system of scholarships, the establishment of girls' hostels, more appointments of female teachers, and women inspectress and the encouragement of more funds towards girls' schools. The commission recommended that 'female education be treated as a legitimate charge alike on local, municipal, and on provincial funds, and receive special encouragement'. Apart from this, it was suggested that government should give liberal grants to private girls' schools (Mukherji, 1951, p167).

Slow Start

The beginning of modern education in the early years was actually started by missionaries. From the historical point of view, women do have not equal opportunities for education. Cruel patriarchy norms, hard social evils, different social customs, poverty, and many other factors contributed in terms of low women's education in India. As mentioned earlier the lack of proper organization of low male-minded thinking did not want to have educated ladies. In the report on the state of education in Bengal (1836) William Adam wrote: 'A superstitious feeling is alleged to exist in the majority of Hindu families, principally cherished by the women and not discouraged by the men, that a girl taught to read and write will soon after marriage become a widow' (Forbes, 2012,p33). This statement of Adam's defines the Indian mindset and also shows that Hindu women totally rely on their male- counterparts, and had to respect their decisions and their quest for knowledge was tantamount to suicide. Having this kind of ideology one can imagine that how our society can grow? Regarding the importance of female education in 1854, Sir Charles Wood in his famous Education Dispatch of 1854 said that: The importance of female education in India cannot be over-rated; and we have observed with pleasure the evidence which is now afforded of an increased desire on the part of many of the natives to give a good education to their daughters. By this means a far greater proportional impulse is imparted to the educational and moral tone of the people than by the education of men'. Dalhousie hailed it as ' the beginning of a great revolution in Indian habits' (Bharati Roy, 2005, p188).

From 1900s onwards: A Period of Westernization and Development

Modern ideas of education for women began at the end of the eighteenth century. Although progress was extremely slow till 1921 when education was handed over to Indian ministers in the provincial administration. Through the efforts of missionaries and social reformers a special emphasis made on women's education.

Table no. 1: Increment in the number of colleges for women.

	1901-02	1886-87
Madras	35	16
Bombay	30	18
Bengal	55	33
United provinces	49	15
Burma	8	5

Source: S. Bhattacharya, 2001, p.325

Figures from the data show an increment in the number of colleges for women. Some of the women achieved the degree. So, this is a somewhat noteworthy achievement in terms of women's education. The female literacy rate crept from 0.2 percent in 1881 to 1.8 percent in 1921 (Kamat,1976, p4). Maximum numbers of girls were enrolled at the primary level, as this was also a necessary thing because somewhere girls are not get enrolled at the primary level. In 1921 out of a total of 12.24 lakh girls on the rolls, only 26 thousand were enrolled in secondary schools and less than a thousand in colleges (Kamat,1976, p4). Somewhat a substantial advancement was made in terms of women's education.

Table no. 2 given below shows the number of girls in the high, and middle stages of secondary schools:-

Provinces	High	Middle	Total
Madras	491	3575	4066
Bombay	610	1389	1999
Bengal	230	884	1114
United Provinces	154	716	870
Punjab	80	547	627
NWFP	-	-	-
Burma	85	650	735
Central Province	24	305	329
Assam	2	20	22
Berar	1	43	44
Coorg	-	4	4
Total for 1901-1902	1677	8133	9810

Total 1896-1897	1190	7178	8368
-----------------	------	------	------

Source: R. Nathan, Progress of Education in India, 1897-98 to 1901-02

The figures show a remarkable expansion of women's education in terms of High and Middle schools. Undoubtedly, the start was slow in terms of women's education but with the passage of time, an advancement was seen. Progress can be seen in these provinces but not very satisfactory. Later on in the year 1909-10, 1910-11, 1911-12, 1912-13, and 1913-14, the number of institutions for females was 58, 61, 72, 73, and 85 for respectively years. The number of female scholars in 1909-10 was 58, in 1910-11 was 61, in 1911-12 was 72, in 1912-13 was 73. Although the statistics recorded of the education of Indian girls are in no way remarkable². Different finances of the central and local governments of India at the present time preclude any hope of striking educational developments in the immediate future. Further expansion was made by the opening of different Universities and different colleges in different provinces.

The next important step was taken by the Government Resolution of Education Policy, 1913, in context of female education: ' The education of girls remains to be organized. Peculiar difficulties were encountered in this branch of education owing to the social customs of the people. Liberal treatment had been accorded to girls in respect of scholarships and fees. This policy had been continued. Opening of different institutions in different provinces shows a keen development in terms of education.

Table no. 3: total numbers of students in different institutions.

	Government	Board	Aided	Unaided	Total
1921-22 Institutions	42	2	85	23	152
Scholars	10784	226	23737	10477	45224
1916-17 Institutions	30	4	69	22	125
Scholars	10547	456	23738	11696	46437

Source: J. A. Richey, Progress of Education 1917-22, Vol. I

As table no. 3 mentioned above shows the total number of students (45224), and among them 1263 are women. The enrolment of women shows an increase of 50 percent³. The different statistical figures show the involvement of women in different art colleges, science colleges, and many more. These data show that somewhere now Indian public opinion is slowly changing from its former attitude of positive dislike to the education of women and is

progressing from apathy to cordial co-operation⁴. These growing figures of women itself show the demand of women in secondary and also in higher institutions. The education of girls had been always on lower ranking as compared to boys, and this reacted adversely to the progress of female education. Apart from this one reason came out that some evoke parents do send their daughters to school to become literate and had had better prospects in the marriage market as compared to illiterate girls. Some sections of the parents also educate their girls for the sake of employment as teachers but they are very microbe in numbers. Now education has some value in the marriage market. The demand for female education among the people has been on the increase from year to year.

Table no. 4: Enrolment of Girls by Institutions

Year	In Arts College	In High school	In middle schools	In Primary Schools	In special Institution	In Unrecognised Institution	Total enrolment
1921-22	938	25130	85079	1195892	11184	77580	1395803
1926-27	1624	39858	123892	1545963	14729	90745	1816811
1931-32	2966	75479	170997	2073141	18981	123120	2464641
1936-37	6039	114481	216965	2607088	23027	138833	3107654
Increase. between 1922-27	686	14728	38813	350071	3545	13165	421008
Increase. between 1927-32	1342	35621	47105	527178	4252	32375	647830
Increase. between 1932-37	3073	39002	45968	533945	4046	15713	643013

Source: John Sargent, Progress of education in India 1932-37.

The figures are revealing in themselves towards the progress of girls' education in India in all stages. In the coming years, up to before independence, there has been an increase in the number of all types of institutions for girls.

Critical Analysis

From the above brief analysis, it could be assumed that some progress was achieved in terms of women's education in the pre-independence period, now we shall try to probe it further, subject it to critical analysis and list out the various achievements and inadequacy as well as others socially significant features.

In primary education, earlier Wood's Despatch and Hunter Commission made a special focus on this area. Later on in the coming years with the District Board Primary Education Act of 1926, several changes are made in the enrolment of girls in primary education. Primary education was the main attraction of development in the Educational field, as it is considered the basic and first step towards the progress of education. Serious shortfall in terms of primary education as it is well-known, is due to the low enrolment among the weaker section of society. In some of the provinces in spite of the several acts girl's education made a hard beginning. Major of small girls sometimes do not get enrolled in primary education. Thus, along with the slow rise in female literacy, the total number of illiterate women is also increasing from year to year. Again, whatever progress has been achieved before pre-independent India in terms of female literacy or women's education is extremely uneven. The gains in, in fact of most education, mostly benefitted the upper class, and advanced class (especially boys).

Class Obstacles

There have been several obstacles regarding the development of women's education. The causes for low rates of female education were many, and we will summarize them very briefly here. There was no incentive for women's education. Several factors contributed to the low female literacy rate in India. In pre-independent India, Indian society was under the chain of different social taboos. The immediate problem in the education of girls is one of social development. The prevalent different customs and ideas opposed to the education of girls will require different handling in different parts of India.

The patriarchal nature of the society did not allow women for more education. The concept of 'EDUCATION' was not meant for them. Women are comparatively weak and due to the tyranny of social customs they were under the subordination of men. Owing to this weakness and domination by men, they have to spend their lives in ignominy and subordination (Forbes, 2005, p12).

During the colonial era, women lived the life of puppets. Due to the existence of several evils, they even are not allowed to breathe properly. They only victims of this evil. Because of this not much attention was paid towards their education. There is a great desire of good mothers, and good wives rather than an educated lady⁵. So, in short purdah, patriarchy, early marriage, and poverty are the major barrier to women's education. All these make very less attendance of girls in the schools.

A women's role was only confined to looking after the home, children, and husband. It was held that by offering women the opportunity for education 'society would merely suffer'. Actually, there was the practical typical orthodox misperception among the people that once girls started attending schools, they would become discontented with their traditional role in life. The education of girls is confronted with two major problems. First, it cost too much for the education of girls, as schools are at very distant places from their locality. Secondly, for economic reasons, the education of boys is more preferred as compared to girls. Mainly the domestic chores tend to bind the girls to the four walls of the home. They often helped their mothers. Parents are also not educated about the benefits of girls' education and even find the education of girls as a doubly expensive thing to carry forward. All these factors somewhere contributed to less percentage of girls at an early phase. The percentage of women in higher institutions is very less as compared to boys.

Traditionalism v/s Modernism

The typical Indian society had a heavy dose of tradition in women's life. It acts as an important source of inequality and discrimination between the education of women and men in society. Boys were educated but very less attention was paid to the women. The traditional patriarchal ideology and different social taboos did not allow women to move further in their life. Or, in other words, it can be said that tradition has been in India, as carriers of patriarchal ideologies. Both tradition and modernity are eminently colonial constructs (Sangari and Vaid, 1989, p23). Changes have continued to occur in the form of modernization, in the form of thinking, mindset, and many areas, but the journey was not an easy task. Direct attention toward modern education led to the new Indian intelligentsia. The firm believes modern education led them to focus on the importance of education and its necessity to achieve any reform not only in terms of the conditions and status of women but also in terms of society at large. The long duration and resilience of patriarchal practices make the matter more complex (Sangari and Vaid, 1989, p23). Breaking all these different sets of ideologies was not an easy job.

With the help of different reformers, missionaries, and intellectuals and several women's movements, made women's entry into the different public spheres. Modernization or moderate thinking or scientific thinking began to develop from the mid of the eighteenth century and slowly-slowly process move on. The history of modernizing women was

undertaken by several efforts and also by inspiring reformers. Reforming women's questions thus became a crucial tool in the colonial ideology.

During the colonial era, women were in the grip of many social evils like Sati, Pardah, Widowhood, Early marriage, and Female infanticide, evils like these really pushed back a step from modernizing themselves in life. It took several decades to get rid out of this chain. In the context of the women's question, the entire focus had been on how to uplift their status. At the beginning of the twentieth century the experience of the nineteenth century, especially in its second half, in terms of the formation of women's identity (Sangari and Vaid, 1989,p102). Women become emblematic of tradition and the reworking of tradition is largely conducted through debating the rights and status of women in society. Despite this intimate connection between women and tradition, or perhaps because of it, these debates are in some sense not primarily about women but about what constitutes authentic cultural tradition (Sangari and Vaid, 1989,p118). On the whole, women were the equation of tradition with scriptures. Women somehow become sites upon which various versions of scriptures and traditions are elaborated and contested. Different social evils were a modern discourse on tradition. 'Tradition' is sometimes combined with 'religion' and 'culture'.

Debates on women's education, Sati, and widow- remarriage regarding women, were not merely for them, but also instances in which the ethical challenge of colonial rule was confronted. Women always came to be as representatives of 'tradition' who were always viewed as the 'weaker sex' and deluded creatures.

A Ray of Awareness

In pre-Independent India, the image of the woman was as a housewife or homemaker. In short, to them, a good housewife, and good mother was the thinking of their male counterparts⁶. Educated men did not want to have educated ladies around them. Total attention was paid to the boys. Conservatism, caste, early marriage, and purdah, are given as the causes of the backwardness of women's education⁷. In short, no one can deny that these cruel evils are a natural result of illiteracy and ignorance of our Indian women and also affect their growth in terms of education. It is the old ideal of women's activity- that is responsible to a great extent for the slower progress of women's education not only in society, or in India, but throughout the world.

The advent of modern education also brought with it an advancement in thinking, and also in the concept of freedom and dignity of the individual. The ideas of social reform and social revival also sprouted the ideas of social liberation: in the case of the woman, her liberation, emancipation, growth, or development. It is true they were incipient and exceptional: nonetheless the seed was planted (Kamat,1976,p12). Looking at female education and its products which came into fruitful results from the nineteenth century, one can begin to answer the question of how far female education had achieved the results desired by the two groups who had promoted and advanced it mainly: intellectual persons, educated social reformers. With the inculcation of modernization, there is somewhat freedom of living and freedom of thought in the coming years and after Independence.

Basically, all the early well-wishers of women's education felt that education was necessary to make them better spouses for men with modern education. C S Lakshmi summarized it by saying, ' the educated women will be ministers to men, secretaries at home, accountants at home, efficient watchmen, good cooks, make conversation that would please men;..... she would combine the admirable qualities of a European lady with her own Indian qualities if she were educated.....' (Kamat,1976,p12). These lines show the benefits of women's education in our country. As this was the basic assumption that if full attention was paid to their education, then there would be an entirely different system.

Up to the end of the pre-independence era, there was the awakening of consciousness among the women related to education and also the desire to change their role as what was there earlier. It seems real effective change among them. Towards the mid of the twentieth century, there was a change in the women's role. It is well-known that education is an important part of their life. Modern education made an impact on women's occupations.

Social Change and Progress

After analysing educational progress, now this section deal with the social change that arrived in women's lives from the mid-nineteenth century onwards. Social change is an important aspect that has accompanied the progress of women's education during this period. Before the arrival of Independence, during colonial rule, now there were women at every forefront. Now educated women found a voice of their own. They articulated the needs of women, critiqued their society and the foreign rulers, and developed their own institutions. That these institutions were often as conservative as those designed by men should not be taken as a sign that these women wished to preserve the status quo (Forbes,2012,p 61). One of the important

aspects of social change was accompanied by the progress of women's education during this period. Education will always remain the main factor resulting in significant social change and undoubtedly, the changes in all spheres of life.

Nevertheless, in the history of the pre-independence era and with the beginning of modern education in India, education spread awareness and brought the process of social change in the coming years. Education also played a significant role in the process of transition from rigid and orthodox thinking into scientific and rational thinking.

In other words, it was a process of modernization in colonial structure with all its twists and turns. From the different statistics figures it is clear that social changes resulted in the advancement in women's education. Up to the end of the pre-independent era and towards the beginning of a new independence era, changes could easily be observed in the social position of Indian women, and those changes are extremely uneven and differ from region to region. Basically, there have been two aspects regarding the social changes in terms of women. Firstly, there have been changes in the ideas and attitudes in the society which was mainly patriarchal in nature, and secondly, changes in the ideas and attitudes of women among themselves, and also towards their role in the family. This social change not only liberated the ideas but also helps in the emancipation of women. One of the great boons of social changes in women's lives was the eradication of several cruel evils like Sati, child marriage, female infanticide, polygamy, and many more which decayed the lives of hundreds of women. Now- onwards education of girls and women is the motto of 'NEW INDIA'.

Expenditure on women's education

Finally, there is the question of cost. This is the major section related to women's education. Among the different recommendations of the Indian committee, grant in aid rule was also recommended for girls' schools. As they are lacking in terms of funds. Expenditure on female education had always been very slow. Although it had a very slow start and less interest.

As earlier no one took great initiatives regarding women's education. Very less attention was paid to them. Through the Indian Commission, more attention was now paid to women's education regarding primary education, secondary and higher education. Grant-in-aid was given with indiscriminating liberality to all promoters of girls' schools.⁸ Progressed by years and years Indian female education was encouraged by giving higher grants to fulfil all basic needs and also to maintain infrastructure and buildings. Different types of grants were

provided through the government like the maintenance of the infrastructure of buildings and maintenance grants were provided to the girl's schools. In 1915, there was a special grant for female education by the government of India. As there was a distribution of the Government of India's recurring grant of Rs 1,26,000 being the balance available from the grant of Rs1,40,000 for female education⁹. Later on, year-by-year expenditure was made on female education. But somewhere these expenditures are less as compared to boys' schools. The education of an Indian girl cost more according to that of a boy's education. Earlier there are many signs that public opinion realized the weakness of an educational system in which half of the population is allowed to remain illiterate¹⁰. In the coming years, many funds were made to spend in the form of women's education. As different agencies show a genuine interest in the cause of women's education. Women's education largely depends on-nongovernment funding, different charitable trusts, some private endowments, several missionary societies, and many more till 1947, nevertheless, the majority of the initiatives in this field came from Indians.

Provisions of Curriculum

Implementation of the right curriculum has always been an important issue in terms of the growth of women's education and continuously redefines many times. The current curriculum does not meet the correct expectations of girls. There was a lot of differences between girls' and boys' curriculum. Western style of education was meant for boys but not for girls. Some of the leaders are in favor of it, and some are against it. In fact, the curriculum framed for boys was aimed to get a certain job while girls had only basic things. Some of the schools implement the new additional subjects which could offer special training to the girls, but some oppose it. In some schools, English as a subject was made compulsory but somewhere it does not implement. Few government officials were partly in favor that there should be a desirable change. Few subjects did emerge as 'feminine' for example home science, needlework, and home cooking are not meant for females while others like physics, chemistry, astronomy, and mathematics seem to be 'masculine' subjects as they are only meant for boys. 'Education' must be the need of an hour and the slogan of the day, which is meant for all. The purpose of education must be the same for every individual. The Hunter Commission of 1882 laid emphasis, that the curriculum should be organized according to the needs of the pupils. It was the responsibility of different provincial governments to frame the curriculum. There should be algebra, trigonometry, geography, and medicine, like subjects which would help pupils in their future. The Hunter Commission diverse the curriculum into

two parts, one to prepare the student for further studies and the other to give them the better and best education in their everyday life. Different educationists felt the immediate need for revision in the context of the curriculum regarding girls. There was a feeling of dissatisfaction with the curricula of schools for boys and girls. The content of curricula shows no interest in girls' schools. Music, needlework, and domestic economy were introduced among the optional subjects. Some new courses must be framed in different schools in different provinces. But in recent years the feeling has been growing stronger and stronger that girls now need something to be different, fitting them for the task of efficient home-making, which is going to be the work in the life of the vast majority (Lady Hartog, 1936,p 505).

In short, the cost and lack of qualified teachers related to different subjects are major stumbling blocks. Apart from domestic science, nursing, needlework, cookery, and domestic work, they did not realize the usefulness of the other subjects. The education which the girls are receiving shows that they are bound to confine themselves between the four walls of the house. Some schools at the lower primary stage believe, that there is no need for any change in the curriculum. But at the upper primary stage, there should be provision for girls to have sewing, music, needlework, handicraft, etc. After the age of 11-14 age, some physical training must be provided to them. Sometimes we forget her socio-economic freedom and her services in society. In fact, her contribution to nation development was equally important as that of boys. That is the reason why, while framing the curriculum for girls, we should not forget her careers and dreams outside the home also. Many of the girls wish to take some vocation to the other in addition to homemaking, also they want to use their education for some social work also. For this reason, some vocational education should be introduced in girls' schools.

During, British rule, the focus led towards socialization as the main function of education. The majority were of the opinion that a different curriculum should be there for boys and girls. There is a common view that education should prepare girls to become better wives and mothers. Apart from this, they should be able to pursue their dreams also. The curriculum should include such subjects which enable them to perform their roles better. Regarding gender differences, it has to be admitted that women are psychologically and physically distinct from men. Indian social reformers and political leaders demanded a new curriculum for Indian girls. The majority of them were of the opinion that the girls need to be trained not

only to become trained housewives but also better educationists. However, the major function of education is to develop scientific thinking in one's individual mind.

Pioneers Efforts

According to my opinion, the development of women's education is incomplete without discussing the role of different pioneers who made different sacrifices to uplift women as socially, economically, emotionally, and educationally. The efforts made by reformers, missionaries, and intellectual persons for ameliorating women's conditions did not go unnoticed. While male reformers had been working for women's education also. Women, who initially too suppressed and had subordinate status. They were deeply committed to this field and also felt it was their duty to educate their mothers and sisters. Social reformers all over India now began started talking, discussing, and in short writing about the benefits of women's education via journals, newspapers, and through different organizations. Now they argued about the welfare of women because educated women would be able to correspond with their husbands. Definitely, educated women would be better and the best housewives. Therefore, education was necessary for enlightened mothers.

For the growth of women's education, many Indian reformers have done a great job in opening a kind of new awareness in women. The list includes many reformers who uphold their own unique qualities and contribution regarding women's education and growth in their social status. Firstly, the Brahmo Samaj, and later the Prarthana Samaj, Arya Samaj, and Theosophical society all supported women's education and bring a lot of changes. Indians supported female education because they wanted social and religious reform or social and financial mobility, or both in the case of women (Forbes,2012, p41).

The name of Raja Ram Mohan Roy is usually listed first among those of nineteenth-century reformers who were concerned and aimed to improve women's condition and status, and he was later on called as 'Father of Modern India'. His tireless effort in banning Sati, a cruel evil against women, becomes a milestone in modern history and inspired others to do some better for the welfare of women. 'Social Reform' became an important issue.

Rammohan Roy, Pandit Vidyasagar, Swami Dayanand Saraswati and many others were trained in Hindu classics and saw India as recovering from a dark age. They argued that there had been a "golden age" where women were valued more and respected in societies. But after the decline of the golden age, the status of women also degraded and lost somewhere. By the

second half of the nineteenth century, there were reforms in every nook of India. They focussed attention on Sati, female infanticide, polygyny, child marriage, purdah, prohibitions on women's education and many more. All these social evils and the general indifference of parents regarding the education of their daughters. From a very early age girls were not required to be independent children, in short, they are bound in the chains of customs and domestic duties. There was a stern seclusion of women. All these starting points are the major source of girls which secluded them to sit at home.

Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar championed female education. In Northern India, Swami Dayanand Saraswati, the founder of the Arya Samaj, encouraged female education and condemned customs he regarded as degrading to women: marriages between partners of unequal ages, dowry, and polygyny (Forbes,2012,p20). Child marriage among all evils was widely prevalent among different provinces of India, in short among all types of castes and communities in the early years of the nineteenth century. Strong and deeply rooted prejudices consider women's education as an unnecessary part of their life.

Pandita Ramabai was the first Indian woman who publicly took women's education as her main propagating issue. She was a young widow herself, instead of being a widow Ramabai wanted all women, to be self-supporting and self-economically independent especially widows. Time the time she focussed only on one agenda to educate whole Indian women and sisters while she believes that the salvation of women lay in their own hands and that for their liberation they should not depend on the menfolk. She firmly believed in women's independence. Pandita Ramabai Saraswati, founder of the Sharda Sadan in Bombay and Poona (1889). Mataji Tapaswini who began the Mahakali Patshala of Calcutta (1893), and D.K. Karve who began a school for widows in Poona (1896), all represent their efforts to build many schools and colleges for women. Professor Karve founded The Indian Women's University at Poona is an excellent example of the advancement of women in terms of their educational development. During the 1890's he established a number of schools for girls in Poona. Later on, he opened a home for widows. It really sorts out the different problems for women. In short, they can now pursue or forward their higher education. He believed that widows needed an education 'that would make them economically independent and would enable them to think for themselves' (Forbes,2012,52). The contribution of Mahatma Gandhi also had great significance. He has advocated the equality of men and women. A passionate lover of humanity, and an implacable foe of injustice, Gandhiji led a great impact on women's lives and bring them to the forefront. Meanwhile, he several times had spoken out

fearlessly against enforced widowhood, purdah, prostitution, child marriage, dowry system, and economic bondage.

The first All India Women's Educational Conference, held in 1927 not only reiterated demands for equality of educational facilities but also demands for the education of women and about the upliftment of their social position. Distinguished reformers like - Sarojini Naidu, Mrs. Annie Beasant, Raj Kumari Amrit Kaur, Mahatma Gandhi, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar, Lala Lajpat Rai, and many more Indian reformers did a lot of efforts in the context of women education. many of them supported through their constant work and leadership contributed a lot towards the upliftment of women socially, emotionally, and educationally. Efforts of each reformer brought women from all over India who confined themselves to the house. Women not only of the reformed families but the illiterate, rural women, rich or poor everybody now is an enlightened individual. Education of women came to be a public issue opposition to it notwithstanding. The slogan of social reformers by this time had become " Educating a girl means educating a family". Women's education was essential for national development.

Conclusion

By the turn of the century and up to the coming of Independence the number of schools for girls and school enrolment had risen dramatically. There were educational institutions for women in all parts of the country, and enrolments tripled and quintupled at school and Universities level. Between 1920 and 1940 'new woman' was seen everywhere, a woman who is more confident, and aware. The demand for women's education was growing steadily. These 'new women' learned where the boundaries were and just how far they could go. Education is considered to be 'the agent of basic change in the status of women'. It has to be recognized the fact that women play a special role in society and without their participation a country's development is incomplete. A woman is an important human being like a man. This whole was an energetic process that included educated women. Looking towards women's education and its products in the twentieth century were incomparable and the results desired by the different groups of people who took a great initiative towards women's education.

Declaration of Conflicting Interests

The author declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/ or publication of this article.

Funding

The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and or publication of this article.

Notes:

1. Department of Statistics India, Statistical Abstract For British India, Vol V Education, 1913-14, Calcutta, 1915.
2. Richey, J.A(1923). Progress of Education in India 1917-22, Eight Quinquennial Review, Vol.1, Calcutta.
3. Ibid., p 68.
4. Ibid., p. 129.
5. File no. 85/ 1916, Emprovement of Female Education, Education Department, UPSA.
6. Ibid.
7. Singh, Gurumukh.(1920) The Education of Girls, Indian Review, p.297.
8. File no. 23/1884, Report of the Indian Education Commission, Education Department, UPSA9.
9. File no. 4/1915, Government of India's Special Grant for Female Education, Education Deptt., UPSA.
10. Richey. J.A., Progress of Education in India 1917-22, Eighth Quinquennial Review, Vol.1,p.139.

References

1. Bhattacharya, Sabyasachi.(2001). *The Development of Women's Education in India: A Collection of Documents 1850-1920*, New Delhi: Kanishka Publisher
2. Forbes, Geraldine (2005). *Women in Colonial India*. New Delhi: Chronicles Books.
3. Forbe, Geraldine (2012). *Women in Modern India*. Cambridge University Press.
4. Hartog, Lady (1936). *The Education of Girls in India*. Journal Of The Royal Society of Arts, Vol.84. No.4348,,pp . 499-517.
5. Hauswrith, Frieda.(1932). *Purdah: The Status of Indian Women*. London.
6. Kamat, A.R.(1976) *Women's Education and Social Change in India*, Social Scientist, Vol.5.No.1, pp. 3-27.
7. Mukherji, S.N.(1951) *History of Education in India*. Baroda: Acharya Book Depo.
8. Rao, Parimala. V.(2014) *New Perspective in the History of Indian Education*. New Delhi: Orient Blackswan.
9. Roy, Bharati. (ed.) (2005) *Women of India: Colonial and Post-Colonial Periods*. New Delhi: Sage Publication.

10. Sangari, Kumkum. ed.(1989) *Recasting Women: Essays in Colonial History*. New Delhi: Zubaan.
11. Sen, J. M.(1941) *History of Elementary Education in India*. Calcutta: The Book Company.
12. Women and Education. (1953) UNESCO.